

PREVALENCE AND RISK FACTORS OF CUTANEOUS LEISHMANIASIS IN TEHSIL MUSLIM BAGH DISTRICT KILLA - SAIFULLAH, BALOCHISTAN, PAKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

The study, which examined the occurrence of cutaneous leishmaniasis in people living in Tehsil Muslim Bagh's districts, was conducted between September 2018 and April 2019. Blood samples and skin lesions were used to identify positive cases after suspects were screened for the illness. Samples were mounted so that their trace could be seen. 207 individuals of various ages and sexes were examined in total, however, only 192 (92%) of the suspected cases had the illness verified. A significant portion of patients, 64 percent, were male. The lesion was observed in young people aged 21 to 30 more frequently (31%) than in other groups. In comparison to cheeks (15%), arms (45% male + 20% female), or cheeks (20% male + 0% female), legs were shown to be more infected in both sexes. In the mixed sample, the least contaminated body parts were (4% in males and 5% in females). The most common district for Cutaneous Leishmaniasis was determined to be District East (23.2% male + 8.8% female), followed by District West (10.7% male + 4.3% female), District Central (6.8% male + 5.2% female), District (Nisai) (4.4% male + 6.6% female), and District South (3.8% male + 4.2% female) based on samples from various villages in the Muslim Bagh region.

1. INTRODUCTION.

The parasite *Leishmania* causes the protozoan disease known as cutaneous leishmaniasis, which is contracted through the bite of a female sand fly. These organisms are commonly found in endemic places in people along with the appropriate sand fly vectors; they are typically seen in patients with immune system suppression (Varikuti et al., 2018). Approximately twenty types of *Leishmania* are known to exist and are capable of infecting humans. These microorganisms cause three different clinical diseases: cutaneous, mucocutaneous, and abdominal (CL) leishmaniasis (Nieva et al., 2021). WHO (2017) states that Pakistan, Afghanistan, Albania, and other countries are the most seriously affected by Cutaneous Leishmaniasis (Khan et al., 2021).

Pakistan is continuously vulnerable to several skin diseases, such as leishmaniasis. Unfortunately, until 1935, when a seismic eruption was discovered in Quetta, Pakistan, there was no conclusive evidence of leishmaniasis (Yousuf et al, 2021). The first account of it dates back to 1996 and is from the northern mountainous region. Twenty thousand instances are reported yearly since then. With 11,000 cases, the two Sindh regions of Dadu and Larkana saw the biggest epidemics. In practically every region of Pakistan, cutaneous leishmaniasis is most common (Inceboz 2019).

The poorest people on the planet are usually the ones that get this sickness. In the Eastern Mediterranean, leishmaniasis is a major problem (WHO, 2019). According to reports, the ailment is vector-borne and has been documented in 88 countries globally, of which 16 are developed and 13 are among the 72 developing countries with the least level of development. The seven nations of Syria, Saudi Arabia, Afghanistan, Algeria, Brazil, Iran, and Peru accounted for more than 90% of all cases of CL. The WHO estimates that between 5 and 20 lakh new instances of CL are detected each year, and that 1.2 billion individuals globally are afflicted by the condition (Nawaz et al., 2020).

Leishmaniasis is becoming more common due to a variety of man-made factors, such as urbanization, deforestation, migration, and immunosuppression (Hong et al., 2020). There are three different species of cutaneous leishmaniasis in Pakistan, according to a 2010 WHO report. *Leishmania tropica* produces leishmania major, while *Leishmania infantum* is responsible for zoonotic cutaneous leishmaniasis (ZCL) and zoonotic visceral leishmaniasis (ZVL). Both of these parasites are also the cause of anthroponotic cutaneous leishmaniasis (ACL) (Ghatee, Taylor & Karamian 2020). *Papatasi sergenti* is the carrier used by *Leishmania tropica*, and humans serve as the basin. *Leishmania major* is carried by the Great

gerbil (*Rhombomys opimus*) and the Indian desert gerbil, whereas *Leishmania infantum* is spread by dogs and its vector is unknown.

Cutaneous leishmaniasis is highly prevalent in almost all of Pakistan, including Karachi, KPK, FATA, Punjab, Sindh, and Baluchistan (Ayaz et al., 2018). In six distinct areas of Karachi, one of the biggest cities in the world, data on the prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis and the therapies that are now accessible are to be gathered for the current study.

The chance of developing cutaneous leishmaniasis might be raised by a number of factors. These include living in or traveling to an area that is endemic, particularly if safety measures are not taken to prevent sand fly bites. As they can increase the number of people exposed to sand flies, poverty and unhygienic housing may further increase the danger (Amane et al., 2022). Additionally, persons with compromised immune systems—such as those receiving chemotherapy or living with HIV/AIDS—are more susceptible to contracting the illness. Depending on the *Leishmania* species involved and the patient's immune system, cutaneous leishmaniasis can manifest with a variety of symptoms. The most frequent symptom is a skin lesion, which can occur anywhere on the body but usually occurs where the sand fly bit the victim. a small, painless lump or nodule that sporadically grows into a lesion that has the potential to ulcerate and turn into an open sore with a raised border. In addition to fever, malaise, and other symptoms, the lesion may be surrounded by redness and inflammation (Silveira ET AL.,2009).

Between 0.7 million and 1.2 million new cases of cutaneous leishmaniasis were reported globally in 2010, according to Alvar et al. (2012). These included Afghanistan, Algeria, and other nations with the greatest rates of sickness. According to a study conducted in Iran by Khosravi et al. (2017), the study population's overall prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis was close to 15.5%. Living in rural settings, having a family history of the disease, being male, and having a history of leishmaniasis were risk factors for infection.

According to a comprehensive study and meta-analysis by Amin et al. (2012), In the Middle East, the prevalence of cutaneous leishmaniasis was 5.5%. Saudi Arabia (16.3%) and Iran (17.8%) had the highest incidences. Living in rural locations, having a poor socioeconomic position, and having been to common places in the past were risk factors for infection. According to Al-Ani et al. (2018), 1.5% of the study population had cutaneous leishmaniasis. Living in rural areas, having previously contracted leishmaniasis, and having been to locations where the disease was common were risk factors for infection.

Neira et al. (2022) reported that 6.7% of the population in their inspection study had cutaneous leishmaniasis. Living in rural areas and having a history of leishmaniasis were risk factors for infection.

2. Materials and Methods

A cross-sectional study or investigation relying on surveys was accompanied on the Frequency and Hazard factors of cutaneous leishmaniasis in tehsil Muslim Bagh district Killa Saifullah, Balochistan, Pakistan. The area of district Muslim Bagh (Killa- Saifullah) is 6831km² having a population of 342,814 as of 2017 census. The study was ethically approved by the joint clinical research council of Bolan Medical Complex and University of Balochistan, Quetta. It was carried out in compliance with the Helsinki Declarations for Human Experiments and took place between July 2022 and September 2022. A total of 207 suspected patients with active lesions who frequented the DHQ facility in Muslim Bagh were clinically examined. The patient's name, father's name, sex, age, occupation, location and number of lesions, the date the disease first manifested itself, prior medical history, address, ethnicity, and treatments were all entered into a pre-made proforma. Previous diagnoses made through microscopic examination and/or biopsy tests were also recorded. The patient was interviewed face-to-face to collect information about a number of different factors. Digital cameras or mobile phones were used to capture pictures of the lesion.

2.1. Statistical analysis

The Microsoft Office Excel Suite 2007® was used for the statistical analysis. When there were notable differences, the Student T-test was used. The importance threshold for modifications between men and females, as well as between age groups, infected body parts, and geographic regions, was set at p 0.05.

2.2. Collections of blood and skin biopsy samples

2.2.1. Samples of Biopsy

Samples of skin lesions exhibiting clear signs of skin disease were collected. Before gathering, 100% ethanol was used to clean and sterilize the cutaneous lesions. Between the hand and the first finger, the lesions were punctured. Using a sterile blood lancet, skin scrape samples were collected from the lesion's punctured border and put on one side of the slide. The examination slide had a thick smear on one surface that was fixed in 100% methanol for 30 minutes. Using a permanent marker, the transparencies were stamped with a serial number.

Figure No.1: Samples Taken During Biopsies from Various Bodily Regions

2.2.2. Samples of Blood

Peripheral blood was cautiously injected into the test container using a syringe. The drawn blood samples were spun at a speed of 3000 for 30 minutes. A pipette was used to apply the Buffy coat lightly to the test plates before being immersed in 100% methanol for 30 minutes to repair them. The images were permitted to stain and after air dry before being gently washed with water.

Figure No.2: Blood Samples Taken from Various Body Regions of Infection Sites

2.2.3. Staining and microscopy-based detection

Giemsa-stained skin biopsies and direct parasite detection in impression smears can both be used to identify cutaneous leishmaniasis (Minnat & Al-Bassam 2018). Working Giemsa stain was used for 30 minutes on slides of blood and skin lesions from ill individuals that are dry, thin, and fixed. The slides were stained, then thoroughly cleaned with water, let to air dry, and then dried again. To detect protozoan parasites, the slides were examined with a lens and an oil immersion objective (10 x 100 magnifications) (Leishman Donovan bodies). Leishman-Donovan (LD) corpses discovered in the smear were considered to be reliable proof.

3. Results

A study or investigation on the prevalence and risk factors of cutaneous leishmaniasis was conducted in the district of Muslim Bagh (Killa- Saifullah), Balochistan, Pakistan, among the 207 residents of the various Villages in Muslim Bagh. In the research, a total of 207 individuals were screened; 192 individuals (or 92.75% of the total) tested positive for Cutaneous Leishmaniasis, with 64% of the males (n = 123) and 36% of the females (n = 69) infected shown in Table. 1 and Figure.3.

Table No.1: Occurrence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Gender Wise

Leishmaniasis based on Gender Wise					
Sex	Male	Female	Total	Male %	Female %
Patient's Number	35	20	55	64%	36%

Figure No.3: Occurrence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Gender Wise

They were 0 to 70 years old. The zero denotes the year beginning on the day of birth. As indicated by Table 2 and Figure 2, the age group of 21 to 30 years had the highest prevalence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis (31%), followed by 10 to 19 years (22%), zero to ten years (20%), 30 to 39 years (13%), and the age group of 50 to 59 years (7%).

Table No.2: Incidence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Age Wise

Age	Male	Female	Total	Male Percent	Female Percent
0-9	6	5	11	11%	9%
10-19	7	5	12	13%	9%
20-29	13	4	17	24%	7%
30-39	5	2	7	9%	4%
40-49	1	3	4	2%	5%
50-59	3	1	4	5%	2%
60-69	0	0	0	0%	0%

Figure No.4: Incidence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Age Wise

Both genders exposed bodily parts were discovered to be heavily infected. The lowest percentages of infections were found in the arms (20% male, 0% female), mixed bodily regions (4.4% male, 4.8% female), and forehead (15.3% male, 10.9% female). Legs had the highest percentage of infections (24.8% male, 19.8% female) (Table. 3 and Figure.5).

Table No.3: Body Sections Wise Prevalence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis

Body sites	Male	Female	Total	Male %	Female %
Face	8	6	14	15%	11%
Arms	11	0	11	20%	0%
Legs	14	11	25	25%	20%
Mixed	2	3	5	4%	5%

Figure No.5: Body Sections Wise Prevalence of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis

The majority of the lesions on each patient's body were on exposed areas like the hands, forehead, ankle, arm, ear, and legs. On their legs, limbs, and face, just one patient had more than thirty ulcerative lesions ranging in quantity from one to eight (1-8) lesions on each patient. District (Nisai) (4.4% male + 6.6% female), District West (10.7% male + 4.3% female), District Central (6.8% male + 5.2% female), and District South (3.8% male + 4.2% female) had the lowest prevalence rates of cutaneous leishmaniasis (Table 4 and Figure 6). District East had the highest prevalence rate of the disease. The Muslim Bagh region's several villages provided the samples.

Table No.4: Frequency of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Area Wise

Area	Male	Female	Total	Male %	Female %
East	8	4	12	15%	7%
West	13	5	18	23%	9%
South	2	2	4	4%	4%
Central	4	3	7	7%	5%
Nisai	6	2	8	11%	4%
North	2	4	6	4%	7%

Figure No.6: Frequency of Cutaneous Leishmaniasis in Area Wise

The statistical data demonstrates that there are notable differences in infection between males and girls with infection and significance higher than females ($p < 0.05$). The age ranges of 0 to 10, 11 to 20, 31 to 40, 51 to 60, and 61 to 70 years do not substantially differ from one another in terms of age ($p > 0.05$); however, the age group of 21 to 30 years does differ considerably ($p < 0.05$). Arms are considerably higher in males than females ($p < 0.05$) compared to other body parts, such as the face, legs, and mixed. If we compared the districts of Muslim Bagh, West was considerably higher ($p < 0.05$) than the other villages.

Nearly 68% of males ($n=141$) and 32% of females ($n=66$) were confirmed to have cutaneous leishmaniasis overall. The illness affected people at a higher rate than any other age group: 24% in the 0–10 age range, 23% in the 21–30 age range, 17% in both the 11–20 and 31–40 age ranges, 9% in the 40–50 age range, and 5% in both the 51–60 and the 61–70

age ranges. Both sides' exposed body parts had widespread infections. The face showed the greatest percentage of infections (16% male and 13% female followed by the thighs (18% men, 7% women), the arms (19% men, 7% women), and the mixed body parts (15% men, 5% women). Based on data from Balochistan, the provinces with the next greatest prevalence rates of gender parity are Sindh (20% male, 6% female), Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (15% male, 6% female), Punjab (4% male, 4% female), and Cutaneous Leishmaniasis (34% male, 11% female).

The exposed body parts were where the bulk of the lesions were found. Additionally, patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis were discovered in nearly every district of the city. Younger individuals were more likely to contract the infection than children and the elderly.

4. Discussion

In many tropical nations around the globe, leishmaniasis is an endemic disease. Most members of Asian groups come from underprivileged neighborhoods and lead subpar lifestyles. Such people are more likely to contract vector-borne diseases. Research indicates that leishmaniasis is common not just in Pakistan but also in India, Iran, Afghanistan, and China (Shaheen et al., 2020). The cited literature states that Pakistan has reported on extensive leishmaniasis research from 2003 to 2018 (Mostafavi et al., 2022).

Yousuf et al., (2021) reported more Cutaneous Leishmaniasis instances have been documented from the North West Frontier Province (NWFP) in children and young adults than in persons over the age of 60. They also claimed that men (60.5%) are more likely than women (39.5%) to have the illness. This study is consistent with the ongoing investigation because, as we saw, males were involved in 64% of the 207 cases examined while women were only in 36% of those cases. The ten-year gap between the earlier study and this one demonstrates the persistence of cutaneous leishmaniasis in Pakistan. Khan et al., (2021) investigation from Lower Dir, Pakistan revealed a notable distinction between instances of cutaneous leishmaniasis in males and women. This gender gap can result from the fact that women are usually kept at home while males go to fulfill their responsibilities in the business and workplace. Infection was identified as an important skin condition in 24.5% of men but only 16.1% of women.

However, a previous study by Bhutto et al., (2009) discovered a small change between instances involving men and women. In fact, they investigated the entire country and found that the disease is most severe in the provinces of Sindh and Baluchistan. They claim that the province of Sindh has a significant amount of cases. The diagnostic process,

which involved a smear test and the examination of skin lesions, was the same as the one we used in the current study investigation.

While evaluating the Cutaneous Leishmaniasis patients in Multan, Ahmad et al. (2022) stated that it is a neglected tropical disease. They found 198 patients with cutaneous leishmaniasis, 101 of whom were men and 97 of whom were women, with ages ranging from 10 to 40. In the current case, individuals between the ages of 21 and 30 years old were commonly diagnosed with skin lesions related to Cutaneous leishmaniasis. There may be a small variation in the gender and age distribution between the two regions as a result of environmental factors. Due to population density issues, 32% of the positive instances in the current investigation were only found in district West, while only 8% were found in South.

The province of Sindh continues to be a leishmaniasis focus. In a nationwide survey (Sharif et al., 2017), 94 Sindh province residents tested positive for the illness. The 102 patients whose data they collected represented every region in Pakistan. Leishmaniasis is without a doubt one of the most prevalent skin illnesses in Sindh, according to the literature. It is spreading rapidly and widely.

It appears that *T. indica* in Chabahar has not been particularly susceptible to the Leishmania parasite, or this rodent's biological characteristics have made it less susceptible to the parasite's spread. Another factor preventing this rodent from creating a nest deep enough for sand flies to successfully reproduce and increase their population to the point where they can serve as a helpful vector is a difference in the soil's texture.

Cutaneous leishmaniasis, one of Pakistan's most prevalent vector-borne illnesses, is linked to immunosuppressive conditions like HIV/AIDS, substandard housing conditions, migration, insufficient nutrition, and vector control failures. It mainly affects people with poor incomes. Skinny leishmaniasis cases have been recorded in Pakistan's urban-rural regions of Sindh and Punjab, Azad Jammu and Kashmir, and suburban areas of the Baluchistan province, especially in the native neighboring regions of FATA and KPK (Shaheen et al., 2020). Uninfected areas that border endemic regions are thought to be at risk, and one of the causes of Cutaneous leishmaniasis outbreaks is the colonization of big populations in areas where sandflies are common (Khan et al., 2021).

Here, we suggest applying some non-conventional pesticides to control the vector, particularly since adult flies are active from the final week of August until December and are plentiful then on their breeding grounds.

5. Conclusion

In many parts of the world, cutaneous leishmaniasis is a significant problem for community health. The illness is more prevalent in rural areas, among outdoor workers, and among visitors to endemic regions who do not take the proper measures. Combining several strategies can lower the chance of infection, including vector control, early diagnosis and treatment, public awareness campaigns, and bettering living conditions and access to healthcare. Combinations of interventions that focus on the vectors and the humans are necessary for the effective prevention and management of cutaneous leishmaniasis. These include implementing public health education programmes to increase knowledge of the disease, using insecticides to control sandflies, and improving housing conditions. Anti-parasitic drugs are commonly used to treat cutaneous leishmaniasis; however, their efficacy varies according on the type of parasite and the immunological status of the patient. To eliminate the lesion in some circumstances, surgery may also be necessary. Overall, cutaneous leishmaniasis continues to have a big impact, so attempts to stop and manage the illness must be made. To lessen the effects of this ignored tropical disease, more study is required. New treatment options and preventative measures must also be developed.

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